

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B497		
Date:	17/1/10		
Take Off:	11:00:59Z	Z	Z
Landing:	16:23:50Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	5h 22m51s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: CONSTRAIN

Operating Area: North Sea / North East Scotland

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Richard Cotton	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics / AVAPS training	Angela Dean	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	FAAM
9	CVI	Paul Barratt	Met Office
10	CVI/Mission Scientist Training	Kirsty McBeath	Met Office
11	Mission 2	Keith Bower	Manchester Uni
12	Aries	Clare Lee	Met Office
13	Mini-LIDAR training	Franco Marengo	Met Office
14	Mini-Lidar	Dave Pollard	Met Office
15	Manchester Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester Uni
16	AMS	Paul Williams	Manchester Uni
17			
18			
19			

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
	Met Office 0600 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
	De-brief
	ViRC chat log
	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
Y	Pre-flight log
Y	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
Y	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
Y	Screengrabs (inc Weather Radar)
	Planning charts or plots
Y	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2010-01-17	Alan Woolley	Initial version
R1			
r2			

11:11:22-16:25:28

B497 17 Jan 2010 CONSTRAIN Flight 1

Sortie S4: Snow evolution in deep Altostratus and Cirrostratus.

Deep Altostratus and Cirrostratus layers associated with cold fronts are required for observations of snow evolution when aggregation and sedimentation dominates the cloud evolution rather than ice nucleation or dynamics.

Ice crystal shape or capacitance factor controls how efficiently the ice crystal acts as a source or sink of water vapour. Depositional growth rate.

Weather

Altostratus and cirrostratus associated with cold front, don't want convection.

Sortie location

Northeast coast.

Sortie summary

Perform a Lagrangian descent during which the aircraft drifts with the horizontal wind and descending at a rate similar to the mass weighted fallspeed of snow particles.

Lagrangian descent over few km.

Sortie detail

- 1) **Transit** to operating area at best-range speed and altitude (FL200).
- 2) **Profile ascent** through cloud until 1000ft above cloud top. During profile, determine average wind orientation. All runs are orientated across this determined wind direction.
- 3) **Dropsonde run**: Perform straight and level 1000ft above cloud top. Lidar reports cloud top height. Dropsonde.
- 4) Descend into cloud layer.
- 5) **Cloud penetration runs**: Perform a descending Lagrangian descent, drifting with the horizontal wind to repeatedly sample cloud. The flight path is a race-track (one side is a straight and level run (5 min) and the other side is a profile descent (400ft/min). Initial turn direction is specified by mission scientist.
- 6) **Return transit** at best range speed.

Instrument requirements

Dropsonde launch locations critical, must be in region of Lagrangian descent.

CVI operated continuously in Counter-Flow mode. No varying cut-size or changing to aerosol mode.

Nevezorov zeroed once only when at high level early in flight.

Lidar operated to identify cloud base. No varying integration time or changing the display.

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 17.01.10

Flight No: B 497

Pre-Flighter: STEVE COWAN

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
1	✓	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	80% Post Per → 160
2	✓	Core Chemistry	Enter cyl content press	N ₂ = 22 bar CO ₂ /Ar = 10.5 bar
3	✓	Core Chemistry	Driers OK	
4	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
5	✓	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
6	✓	Core Chemistry	All Flows Checked OK	
7	✓	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
8	✓	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
9	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
10	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
11	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
12	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
13	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
14	✓	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
15	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
16	✓	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
17	✓	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
18	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
19	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
20	✓	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
21	✓	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
22	✓	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
23	✓	Satcom C	Checked	In cockpit
24	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
25	x	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	x	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	x	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	x	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
29	✓	3786 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
30	x	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	
31	x	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	
32	x	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	
33	x	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	
34	✓	3786 CPC	Drained	
35	✓	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
36	✓	Core Chemistry	O ₃ /NO _x /CO zeros performed Ok	
<u>External Checks</u>				
37	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
38	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
39	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
40	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
41	✓	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
42	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
43	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
44	x	WAS Bottles	No. fitted and position.	
45	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
46	✓	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
47	✓	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
48	✓	All other covers	Removed	
49	✓	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
50	✓	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
51	✓	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
52	✓	Upper BBRs	Checked & Cleaned	Signed
53	✓	ICEX	applied	
54	✓	Turb Probe - Traps	emptied, detail contents -	
				a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B497

Date: 17/1/10

Project:CONSTRAIN

Location:NE Scotland

Start	End			
Time	Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg Comments
----	----	-----	-----	-----
105036		startup	0.09 kft	120
105312		qnh 1011	0.09 kft	120
105451		asp open	0.09 kft	120
110059		T/O	0.07 kft	120
111603	112922	Run 1	23.0 kft	038
112221		jw/nevz zero	23.0 kft	328
112926	113156	Profile 1	23.0 - 21.0 kft	307
113156	113403	Run 2	21.0 kft	257
113414	113620	Run 2.1	21.1 kft	339 220kt
113640	113843	Run 2.2	21.0 kft	337 230 kts
113907	114122	Run 2.3	21.1 - 21.0 kft	339 240kts
114207	114404	Run 2.4	21.1 - 21.0 kft	338 250kts
114415	115239	Profile 2	21.2 - 28.0 kft	337
115628	120122	Run 3.1	28.0 - 28.1 kft	175
115850		Sonde 1	28.0 kft	173
120349	120855	Profile 3	28.1 - 26.0 kft	351
120634		lost mpds	26.1 kft	356
121049	121553	Run 3.2	26.1 - 26.0 kft	162
121749	122300	Profile 3.2	26.1 - 24.0 kft	345
122448	122948	Run 3.3	24.1 - 24.0 kft	167
123138	123702	Profile 3.3	24.1 - 22.0 kft	343
123852	124352	Run 3.4	22.0 kft	163
124540	125105	Profile 3.4	22.1 - 20.0 kft	344
125255	125747	Run 3.5	20.0 kft	170
125930	130441	Profile 3.5	20.1 - 18.0 kft	344
130626	131458	Run 3.6	18.1 - 18.0 kft	172
131458	132442	Profile 4	21.5 - 30.0 kft	233
132457	133147	Run 4.1	30.0 - 29.4 kft	351
133058		Sonde 2	30.1 kft	340
133430	133939	Run 5.1	28.1 - 28.0 kft	162
134131	134629	Profile 5.1	28.1 - 26.1 kft	343
134824	135319	Run 5.2	26.1 kft	167
135513	140026	Profile 5.2	26.0 - 24.0 kft	342

140213	140711	Run 5.3	24.1 - 24.0 kft	161
140900	141438	Profile 5.3	24.1 - 22.1 kft	345
141637	142130	Run 5.4	22.0 kft	173
142312	142817	Profile 5.4	22.1 - 20.1 kft	342
143003	143502	Run 5.5	20.0 - 20.1 kft	166
143646	144148	Profile 5.5	20.1 - 18.0 kft	342
144345	144920	Run 5.6	18.0 kft	175
145055	145633	Profile 5.6	18.1 - 16.0 kft	344
145815	150309	Run 5.7	16.0 kft	167
150437	150915	Profile 5.7	16.0 - 14.0 kft	338
151108	151615	Run 5.8	14.0 kft	162
151748	152253	Profile 5.8	14.0 - 12.1 kft	342
152427	152929	Run 5.9	12.0 - 12.1 kft	160
152937	154123	Profile 6	12.2 - 24.0 kft	175 200kts
154123	154449	Run 6.1	24.0 kft	261 200kts
154503	154723	Profile 7	24.0 - 22.0 kft	262 200kts
154724	154844	Run 7.1	22.0 kft	261 200kts
154850	155045	Profile 8	22.0 - 20.0 kft	239 200kts
155045	155410	Run 8.1	20.0 kft	219 210kts
155421	155617	Run 8.2	20.0 kft	216 220kts
155627	155837	Run 8.3	20.0 kft	216 230kts
155857	160058	Run 8.4	20.0 - 20.1 kft	216 240kts
160124	160405	Run 8.5	20.1 kft	216 250kts
162350	Land		0.02 kft	121

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B497

Date: 17 Jan 10

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC only
2. FAAMCPC flooded
3. AMS U/S

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom

MPDS –

Satcom H –

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

ARIES flight log

Flight: B497

page 1 of 3

Date: 17/01/10

Operator(s): CLARE LEE

Res: km⁻¹

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CONSTRAIN (NE Scotland)

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
11:00	T70			closed			
11:02					71	31	
11:07	transit ascent			closed	71.1	30.5	HC Cal 1min
11:16:03	Run 1	CNZ30		open	70.8	30.8	CANAR NZ 30s 30s CH, 30s N, 30s Z continues. FL 230 (220 knots) Hazy but no cloud above or below
11:21	Gentle turn to left.						
11:22							Over Sea S+L clear sky above
11:27							Over land
11:29							left turn towards cloud.
11:29:22	R1 end. P1 ↓						
11:31	P1 end	FL 210					In cloud. (Ci)
11:33:04	R2 end R2.1				70.9	31.0	Runs at diff. air speeds for change angle of attack for CN.
	R2.4						
11:44:15	P2 ↑				70.8	30.3	Climbing through Ci
11:48							Zenith data looking odd during ascent.
		N long		closed	71	30.8	Nadir long 3min N, 1min CH (containing.)
11:50							
11:53	FL 280	CNZ30		open	70.8	30	CANAR NZ 30s continues. fuzzy Ci above. Mainly land below.
11:56:28	R3.1						(contains pic → vertical lines (ice falling out). continues)
12:03	P ↓				70.8	29.7	In Ci - deep below (nadir saturates)
12:16					70.8	30.3	Gentle turns + descents for in-situ spiral.

ARIES flight log

Flight: B497

page 2 of 3

Date: 17/01/10

Operator(s): CLARE LEE

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CONSTRAN CN

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
17:23	P end.						Contrailing 3 intermittent Patches Ci on lidar
12:26:48	Rm 3			0	70.8	30.9	FC240.
17:31							In Ci - deep below, thinner above.
17:31:38	P3 ↓						
	P3 end			0	70.5	30.8	FC220 T = -40°
17:39							Can see grand thro' Ci + thin above Increasing with location. No contrails
17:41							Thick cloud below now
17:49							Ci thinner above + below.
17:51							Thinner still.
17:55	FL200						Thin below, thicker above
18:02							Thinning at again.
18:07	FL180			0	71.	29.7	Below cloud.
18:09							Starting to go back into cloud, but lidar not showing
18:11	climbing						into deep thick Ci seeing layers on lidar.
18:20	FL280 +climbing.						Contrailing
18:24	FL300						Above Ci
18:30	Quick descent into cloud top.						
18:33	FL281						large contrails
18:34:01	11.						

ARIES flight log

Flight: B497

page 3 of 3

Date: 17/01/10

Operator(s): CLARE LEE

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CONSTRAN (NE SCOTLAND)

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
14:02	FL260			0	70.6	31.4	Thick Ci above + below.
14:14	FL300						FL220 in cloud, can just see surface maintains
14:26							In v. thick Ci - signals saturating (not water according to in-situ)
14:37	↓ descents + spirals						FL197 starting to see H_2O on CPL. Lidar sat. below
14:56	FL60			0	70.7	31.1	Thinner below → ARIES signature coming back.
15:05	FL150			0	70.9	31.2	Sea surface - low waves (no white caps). Ci thin below (~3kft only)
15:13							Data stopped collecting.
	FL140	CN230		0	70.8	31.0	Re-started. CAMFR NZ 30s. Pretty much clear below.
15:27	FL120						Out of ci (below it)
15:31							Over sea for most of previous runs.
15:35							Sea lower than cloud below. Ci above.
15:36				0	70.7	30.8	Base of Ci - started snowing
15:44							Intermittent contrails Good vortex shapes.
15:47							Cloud below over maintains clear above.
15:48.45							Into thin Ci (above + below)
15:55							Going through thin Ci, with thick layer above. STW 78 below.

16:04 End Science.

C

Doing CVI speed log/angle attack charts.

Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
Stand-by

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
Test

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Flight Summary B495

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
PCASP	18:35:50	298	0.16kft	52.8N	1.3W						recording started
GIN	18:36:12	298	0.16kft	52.8N	1.3W						started
Buck	18:43:57	066	0.16kft	52.8N	1.3W						started
buck	18:57:58	065	0.16kft	52.8N	1.3W						off
Buck	19:18:59	066	0.16kft	52.8N	1.3W						started, recording (ht)
ASP	19:39:10	351	0.17kft	52.8N	1.3W						open.
T/O	19:39:36	047	0.18kft	52.8N	1.3W						East Midlands
Profile 1	19:39:49	086	0.18kft	52.8N	1.3W	19:52:17	063	10.0kft	53.0N	1.1W	
!	19:47:03	292	1.9kft	52.8N	1.4W						t/o & start p1 194604
cpc	19:48:17	008	3.5kft	52.9N	1.4W						started
sp200	19:49:07	065	4.4kft	52.9N	1.4W						heater on
JW	19:49:17	066	4.8kft	52.9N	1.4W						on
Run 1.1	19:52:17	063	10.0kft	53.0N	1.1W	20:04:37	059	10.0kft	53.4N	0.3E	
nev	19:54:32	060	10.0kft	53.1N	0.8W						zero
jw	19:54:51	061	10.0kft	53.1N	0.8W						zero
heiman	19:56:49	062	10.0kft	53.2N	0.5W						cal 03
psap	19:57:46	063	10.0kft	53.2N	0.4W						flow on
Profile 2	20:04:38	059	10.0kft	53.4N	0.3E	20:12:28	312	1.5kft	53.7N	0.9E	
Run 2.1	20:12:28	312	1.5kft	53.7N	0.9E						
qnh	20:12:58	313	1.5kft	53.7N	0.9E						1017
!	20:29:41	308	1.5kft	54.4N	0.3W						NOx & WAS required reboot

KONUK10272546

Sampling Recording Read a File

Display Range: 00 d 20:34:16
 10 Minutes

(0) CIP Grayscale (1) CIP (2) CDP (3) Hotwire_LWC (4) SPP_200 General_Summary Setup

Pump Relay Control: ON OFF Enable Enabled COM Port 5 No Fault v2.6.7

SPP_200 Data:

Number Conc (# / cm ³)	Sample Flow (vol cm ³ /s)
126.19	0.95
Volume Conc (um ³ / cm ³)	Sheath Flow (vol cm ³ /s)
1.24	13.96
MWD (um)	Laser Ref (V)
0.57	7.56
ED (um)	Electronics Temp (C)
0.39	45.9
Aux Analog 1	Avg Transit
0	1339
Hi Gain Baseline (V)	ADC Overflow
0.03	0
Mid Gain Baseline (V)	
0.35	
Lo Gain Baseline (V)	
0.31	

Pump Flow OK

SPP_200 # Conc (#/cm³)

SPP_200 Volume Conc (um³/cm³)

Particle Count vs Particle Size (Bins)

Bin	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
Count	.1	.11	.12	.13	.14	.15	.16	.17	.18	.2	.22	.24	.26	.28	.3	.4	.5	.6	.8	1	1.2	1.4	1.6	1.8	2	2.2	2.4	2.6	2.8	3	

Search

Press 958mb

OK

Trusted sites 100%

Flight Summary B495

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
PCASP	18:35:50	298	0.16kft	52.8N	1.3W						recording started
GIN	18:36:12	298	0.16kft	52.8N	1.3W						started
Buck	18:43:57	066	0.16kft	52.8N	1.3W						started
buck	18:57:58	065	0.16kft	52.8N	1.3W						off
Buck	19:18:59	066	0.16kft	52.8N	1.3W						started, recording (ht)
ASP	19:39:10	351	0.17kft	52.8N	1.3W						open.
T/O	19:39:36	047	0.18kft	52.8N	1.3W						East Midlands
Profile 1	19:39:49	086	0.18kft	52.8N	1.3W	19:52:17	063	10.0kft	53.0N	1.1W	
!	19:47:03	292	1.9kft	52.8N	1.4W						t/o & start p1 194604
cpc	19:48:17	008	3.5kft	52.9N	1.4W						started
sp200	19:49:07	065	4.4kft	52.9N	1.4W						heater on
JW	19:49:17	066	4.8kft	52.9N	1.4W						on
Run 1.1	19:52:17	063	10.0kft	53.0N	1.1W	20:04:37	059	10.0kft	53.4N	0.3E	
nev	19:54:32	060	10.0kft	53.1N	0.8W						zero
jw	19:54:51	061	10.0kft	53.1N	0.8W						zero
heiman	19:56:49	062	10.0kft	53.2N	0.5W						cal 03
psap	19:57:46	063	10.0kft	53.2N	0.4W						flow on
Profile 2	20:04:38	059	10.0kft	53.4N	0.3E	20:12:28	312	1.5kft	53.7N	0.9E	
Run 2.1	20:12:28	312	1.5kft	53.7N	0.9E						
qnh	20:12:58	313	1.5kft	53.7N	0.9E						1017
!	20:29:41	308	1.5kft	54.4N	0.3W						NOx & WAS required reboot

KONUK10272546

Sampling Recording Read a File

Display Range: 00 d 20:34:19
 10 Minutes

(0) CIP Grayscale (1) CIP (2) CDP (3) Hotwire_LWC (4) SPP_200 General_Summary Setup

Pump Relay Control: ON OFF
 This light indicates that PADS thinks it has turned the relay on. There is no direct feedback from the probe.

SPP_200 Data:

Number Conc (# / cm ³)	Sample Flow (vol cm ³ /s)
106.21	0.95
Volume Conc (um ³ / cm ³)	Sheath Flow (vol cm ³ /s)
3.25	13.57
MWD (um)	Laser Ref (V)
1.68	7.65
ED (um)	Electronics Temp (C)
0.93	45.9
Aux Analog 1	Avg Transit
0	1462
Hi Gain Baseline (V)	ADC Overflow
0.01	0
Mid Gain Baseline (V)	
0.35	
Lo Gain Baseline (V)	
0.31	

SPP_200 # Conc (#/cm³)

SPP_200 Volume Conc (um³/cm³)

Particle Count

Particle Size Bins

Y-Axis: Auto-Scale Log-Scale Normalized

Pump Flow OK

Search

Press 958mb
eg

OK

Trusted sites 100%

Pump Relay Control
 This light indicates that PADS thinks it has turned the relay on. There is no direct feedback from the probe.
 ON OFF
 Relay On ●

SPP_200 Data

Number Conc (# / cm ³)	Sample Flow (vol cm ³ /s)
158.79	0.95
Volume Conc (um ³ / cm ³)	Sheath Flow (vol cm ³ /s)
2.72	13.8
MVD (um)	Laser Ref (V)
1.45	7.66
ED (um)	Electronics Temp (C)
0.68	45.9
Aux Analog 1	Avg Transit
0	914
Hi Gain Baseline (V)	ADC Overflow
0.04	0
Mid Gain Baseline (V)	Pump Flow OK
0.36	
Lo Gain Baseline (V)	
0.31	

Y-Axis

Auto-Scale ● Log-Scale ● Normalized ●

SS Settings A Temps A Flows A OPC A Monitor A Prog Control

Flow set (Vccm)

500.00

Sample Flow (Vccm)

45.87

Valve Set (V)

3.22851

Sheath flow (Vccm)

451.59

Flow Ratio

9.84

Total flow (Vccm)

497.46

Sample Pressure (mb)

647.06

Air Pump Switch

Air Pump Indicator

Manual Override

Valve Set M (V)

2.50

Liquid Flow Set

Low

Liquid Supply pump

HELP

Status

Date

12/09/09

Time

21:59:43

Current File

CCN-200 data 091209210138.csv

Particle Counter

Particle Counter B

SS Settings B Temps B Flows B OPC B Monitor B Chart

SS 1 B

1st SS B

1.5

Duration 1 B

8

2nd SS B

1.5

Duration 2 B

8

3rd SS B

1.5

Duration 3 B

8

4th SS B

1.5

Duration 4 B

8

5th SS B

1.5

Duration 5 B

8

Auto

Current SS B

0.27

SS Control B

Manual

Manual Input Selection SS set (%)

Delta T SS

0.27

HELP

Flow A Flow B Temperature A Temperature B Numb Conc DMT

Sample

Sheath

Total

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 17 Jan 2010 1100 UTC

